

JOINING PARTICULATE-REINFORCED ALUMINIUM

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ABSTRACT

The diffusion bonding of particulate-reinforced aluminium has been investigated with particular reference to the use of alloy interlayers. Joint strengths have been measured using a shear jig designed to avoid the peel stresses associated with the more conventional lap-shear test. Microstructural characterisation of the bonds, carried out using electron microscopy and electron-probe microanalysis, showed that the magnesium present in the aluminium alloy was a crucial factor in forming a joint. For the composite materials, the bond strength was found to decrease with increase in volume fraction due to the fact that bonding had developed only at regions of metal-to-metal contact. The strength was improved, however, when a thin layer of alloy was interposed between the mating surfaces.

Keywords: Joining, Diffusion bonding, Aluminium, Composites.

1. INTRODUCTION

Diffusion bonding has been used extensively to join metals to themselves and to other metals, as well as to ceramics. The process involves applying pressure to a work-piece held at high temperature, usually contained in an inert gas or low pressure atmosphere to limit the surface oxidation which otherwise inhibits metal diffusion across the interface. The technique works well when bonding titanium because surface oxides and contaminants are dissolvable in the metal at bonding temperatures of ~900°C, but with aluminium the tenacious oxide forms a barrier to bonding. Halide fluxes can be used when welding aluminium in order to dissolve the oxide, although corrosion problems may then arise during service; alternatively, fragmentation of the oxide film by deformation provides a solution. Another approach involves modifying the matrix with elements such as magnesium in order to disrupt the surface oxide via chemical reduction [1], a method which has been used to bond aluminium alloy (8090) reinforced with SiC particulate [2,3], although low strength joints were obtained due to the poor bonding of the reinforcement. The use of an alloy interlayer improved the situation by increasing the effective metal-to-metal contact.

The present paper is concerned with the diffusion bonding in air of particulate-reinforced Al-Cu-Mg (2124) alloy, with and without the use of interlayers of the unreinforced metal. The integrity of the bonds are assessed by shear tests, related to microstructural and fractographic observations, and compared with similar data obtained when bonding unreinforced alloy.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1. Materials

Bonding experiments involved the use of Al-4.2Cu-1.5Mg-0.6Mn (2124) alloy with and without silicon carbide particulate reinforcement. The unreinforced alloy was supplied in the T851 condition, whilst the composite material, manufactured by British Petroleum using the powder metallurgy/extrusion route, was supplied as 25 mm diameter bar. The SiC reinforcement had a nominal size of 3 μm and was present in the composite in volume fractions of 0.25, 0.30, 0.35, and 0.40.

2.2. Diffusion bonding

Specimens were prepared by grinding the surfaces to be bonded using a succession of silicon carbide papers down to 1200 grit. They were then cleaned with Teepol and degreased in acetone. Interlayers for bonding were produced from the as-received 2124 alloy billet by successive rolling and annealing to a thickness of $\sim 200 \mu\text{m}$. Diffusion bonding was carried out using an Instron testing machine fitted with stainless steel platens and incorporating a tube furnace. Prior to bonding the thickness of the sample was measured and this was compared with the value obtained after bonding so that the permanent deformation induced during the operation could be determined. To prevent adhesion to the platen surface the sample was sandwiched between steel shims. The furnace was lowered until the platens were in contact with the sample and the load applied at a rate of 0.5 mm/min to give the required pressure; a constant pressure could not be maintained during the bonding process because of the absence of automatic load compensation for deformation of the specimen.

Diffusion bonding experiments were carried out at 500°C using an initial applied pressure of 10 MPa for 240 minutes.

2.3. Microstructural analysis

Specimens cut from composite plate and from unreinforced metal were metallographically prepared, using progressively finer grades of diamond compound down to 1 μm abrasive. Light microscopy examination was usually followed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Quantitative analysis of the microstructural features in the specimen was carried out using a wavelength dispersive spectrometer (WDS) system fitted to an electron-probe microanalyser (EPMA).

Thin (\sim few 100 nm thickness) sections suitable for transmission electron microscopy (TEM) were prepared from the bond regions by cutting 3 mm diameter discs and mechanically grinding them to a thickness of $\sim 300 \mu\text{m}$. The discs were dimpled on both sides using a VCR model 500 and then thinned by argon bombardment in a Gatan Duomill. TEM examination was carried out in a 200 kV microscope fitted with an EDS system.

2.4. Shear tests and fractography

The shear strength of a bond was determined by carrying out shear tests on a series of coupons cut from the original joint and then averaging the individual data; the off-cuts were set aside for microstructural analysis. The size of test coupon was based upon results obtained on shear testing pressure-welded aluminium [4] which showed a reduced experimental scatter with increase in overlap-to-thickness ratio (w/t) and an almost constant value when $w/t > 0.9$. In the present work the test coupons were ~ 10 mm long (w) and of a thickness (t) to give w/t values of ~ 0.9 for unreinforced alloy and composite joints. Tests were carried out at a cross-head speed of 2 mm/min using a 100 kN Instron machine fitted with the jig shown schematically in Figure 1. The shear strength was calculated from measurement of the failure load and the overlap area of each tested coupon, and the bonded area was established from a study of the fractured surfaces using light and scanning electron microscopy. The specific shear strength for each tested coupon was then calculated using the

relevant failure load and bonded area, and the values averaged to give the mean specific shear strength. As-received materials were tested for purposes of comparison.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Aluminium alloy (2124)

3.1.1. As-received material

Microstructural analysis of as-received alloy showed that it consisted of grains $\sim 100 \mu\text{m}$ in length. Particles several μm in diameter were present, which EPMA indicated were $\text{Al}_{40}\text{Cu}_9\text{Fe}_4\text{Mn}$. TEM/EDS studies located particles in the alloy which were believed to be S' and S (Al_2CuMg) phases, and also dispersoids containing aluminium, copper and manganese which were probably the $\text{Al}_{20}\text{Cu}_2\text{Mn}_3$ phase. The measured shear strength of as-received alloy was $255 \pm 5 \text{ MPa}$.

3.1.2. Bonding without an interlayer

Bonding for 240 minutes using an initial applied pressure of 10 MPa gave a permanent sample deformation of $\sim 2\%$. A polished section, Figure 2, shows grains $\sim 200 \mu\text{m}$ in length. The large ($\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$) phases seen to be present in the alloy were found, using EPMA, to have a similar composition to the $\text{Al}_{40}\text{Cu}_9\text{Fe}_4\text{Mn}$ phase identified in as-received material. Smaller precipitates may also be seen, although these were not analysed as they were beyond the resolution of the EPMA technique ($\sim \text{few } \mu\text{m}^3$). The bond interface is recognisable by a thin, almost continuous layer in the centre of the micrograph. Using TEM, the interface layer was found to contain aluminium, copper and magnesium and was considered to be S phase. Magnesium and oxygen-containing particles were also located, Figures 3a, 3b and 3c. Two types of fine precipitate were located in the alloy. The first was S' phase which forms on {210} planes of the aluminium lattice and has a composition Al_2CuMg . The second precipitate contained aluminium, copper and magnesium and formed on {111} planes of the aluminium lattice, similar to the Ω -type precipitate reported for Al-Cu-Mg alloys heat-treated at 370°C for 5 minutes [5]. The shear strength of the joint was $138 \pm 38 \text{ MPa}$ and the bonded area was $75 \pm 20\%$ to give a specific strength of $185 \pm 10 \text{ MPa}$.

3.2. Aluminium alloy (2124) reinforced with SiC particulate (2124/P)

3.2.1. As-received material

Examination of as-received composite revealed a fairly uniform distribution of silicon carbide particulates ranging in size from $5 \mu\text{m}$ to less than $1 \mu\text{m}$. Thin foil TEM studies showed that the silicon carbide had not reacted to any discernible degree with the aluminium, as evidenced by the 'clean' particle/matrix interfaces. The presence of θ , S and Al-Cu-Mn-Fe phases were identified in the alloy as well as oriented precipitates of θ' and S'. Shear test measurements on as-received composite containing SiC volume fractions of 25%, 30%, 35% and 40% gave strengths of $260 \pm 4 \text{ MPa}$, $278 \pm 4 \text{ MPa}$, $288 \pm 6 \text{ MPa}$ and $289 \pm 33 \text{ MPa}$ respectively.

3.2.2. Bonding without an interlayer

Specimens were bonded at a temperature of 500°C for 240 minutes. Initially, a pressure of $\sim 10 \text{ MPa}$ was applied, to give a specimen deformation of $\sim 2\%$, although this decreased to a steady value of $\sim 2 \text{ MPa}$ over a period of 100 minutes.

A metallographic section of 2124/25P composite bonded for 240 minutes is shown in Figure 4a. Where there was metal-to-metal contact across the interface the bond appeared to be well established, but the bonding was poor between contacting silicon carbide particles, as evidenced by the presence of cracks. The shear strength of the joint was $58 \pm 9 \text{ MPa}$ and failure occurred

essentially at the bonded interface, with the fracture surface, Figure 4b, showing both ductile and brittle failure.

Bonding experiments carried out using composites with volume fractions of 30%, 35% and 40% SiC gave pressure versus time characteristics similar to the above 25% sample. Optical examination indicated that the degree of metal-to-metal contact across the joint decreased with increase in volume fraction of silicon carbide. The shear strengths of the joints were 43 ± 14 MPa, 22 ± 10 MPa and 36 ± 14 MPa, respectively, with failure occurring at the bond interface for all specimens.

The effect of applying different amounts of deformation on joint microstructure and shear strength was investigated using 2124/25P composite material. With deformations of 8%, 13% and 19%, the maximum applied pressure was found to be ~ 10 MPa in each case, a value which is approximately the flow stress of the composite. It was noted that an increase in deformation resulted in greater barrelling of the bonded specimens and an increase in the area of mating surface. A micrograph of the specimen bonded using 19% deformation showed a slightly more uneven bond line than the 2% experiment, due to an increased movement of aluminium and SiC particulate at the interface. For all samples, shear testing resulted in failure at the bond line with strengths of 49 ± 9 MPa, 46 ± 22 MPa and 119 ± 4 MPa, for deformations of 8%, 13% and 19%, respectively.

3.2.3. Bonding with an aluminium alloy (2124) interlayer

Bonding with a 2124 alloy interlayer and an initial pressure of 10 MPa at 500°C for 240 minutes produced $\sim 2\%$ specimen deformation for 2124/30P material. Figure 5 shows clearly the interlayer, EPMA indicating little difference in the concentration of copper and magnesium of the foil and composite matrix, as demonstrated by a uniform hardness across the interlayer. Examination of the bond in the TEM was unsuccessful due to the difficulty of preparing suitably thin samples. The shear strength was 111 ± 46 MPa with failure occurring at one of the interlayer/composite interfaces.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Bonding aluminium alloy (2124)

The joint bonded at 500°C for 240 minutes using an initial pressure of 10 MPa had a planar interface, indicative of a solid-state bond, together with \bar{S} phase (Al_2CuMg) associated with interdiffusion of copper and magnesium from the alloy.

The development of a satisfactory joint under these conditions is attributed to the fact that the surface oxide on the alloy is less stable than that on unalloyed aluminium. In this connection, studies on aluminium-magnesium alloys in air [6] showed that a crystalline oxide is produced at 350°C which forms as particles and tends to disrupt the alumina film. This occurs via one of the following reactions,

$\Delta G^\circ = -140 \text{ kJmol}^{-1}$ at 500°C

$\Delta G^\circ = -280 \text{ kJmol}^{-1}$ at 500°C

The more negative free energy of reaction (2) would favour the formation of the spinel oxide (MgAl_2O_4) but, in reality, the oxidation of aluminium-magnesium alloys is more complex and depends on factors such as alloy composition. In the present work, thin foil TEM revealed particles at the joint interface which were associated with aluminium, magnesium and oxygen although it was difficult to say whether they were MgO or MgAl_2O_4 . The presence of oxide particles at the joint interface is consistent with observations by Maddrell *et al* [1] in work on vacuum diffusion-bonded Al-5 wt% Mg alloy.

Bonding was found to take place only within the central region of the joint ($\sim 75\%$), the lack of bonding in the peripheral regions being attributed to a lower pressure caused by friction at the platen/sample interface [7].

4.2. Aluminium alloy (2124) reinforced with silicon carbide particulate (2124/P)

4.2.1. Bonding without an interlayer

The rapid decrease of pressure in the early stages of bonding may be attributed to microstructural features associated with the presence of the SiC reinforcement. For example, the thermal expansion mismatch between matrix and reinforcement means that composites have a higher dislocation density than unreinforced alloy, and this would lead to more rapid recovery during subsequent high temperature processing.

It was established that the shear strength of bonded joints was inversely proportional to the volume fraction of SiC decreasing from ~60 MPa for 25% SiC to ~35 MPa for 40% SiC. This is attributed to the inhibition of bonding at regions of SiC-to-SiC or SiC-to-metal contact. The bonded area, as given by the total metal-to-metal contact will vary with the degree of overlap of the SiC particulate. An upper-bound value of bonded area is obtained where complete SiC-to-SiC contact occurs, Figure 6a, and a lower-bound value where there is no overlap of SiC, Figure 6b. Assuming that the area fraction of particulate at the surface of a section cut through the composite is equal to the volume fraction of SiC, these metal-to-metal limiting values, A_m , may be defined numerically as $(1-V_f)$ and $(1-2V_f)$, respectively, where V_f is the volume fraction of the SiC. If the strength for 100% bonded area is taken as the specific strength for bonded unreinforced alloy, σ_a (~180 MPa), then the joint strength is given by $\sigma_a \times A_m$. For a 25 vol% SiC composite the predicted upper-bound strength is ~135 MPa and the lower-bound strength is ~90 MPa, assuming that bonding is fully established at all regions of metal-to-metal contact.

Optical examination of bonded composite enables an estimation to be made of the area fraction of metal-to-metal contact at the joint interface and this may be used to predict the shear strength of the joint. Inspection of a section of the bonded 25 vol% sample, Figure 4a, revealed ~40% metal-to-metal contact across the joint interface, to give an estimated shear strength of ~70 MPa. (This assumes that 100% contact area gives a specific strength of 2124 alloy when bonded under similar conditions, ~180 MPa). The predicted value of strength is, however, less than the lower-bound value of ~90 MPa and this may be due to (a) errors introduced during the measurement of the metal-to metal contact or (b) incomplete joint formation at regions of metal-to-metal contact as a result of incomplete breakdown of the oxide film. The strength does, however, compare favourably with the measured value of ~60 MPa.

A similar approach may be used for higher volume fraction composites. The upper- and lower-bound shear strength values for the composites with SiC volume fractions of 30%, 35% and 40% are illustrated graphically in Figure 7, along with estimated strengths. The measured shear strengths are generally less than the lower-bound values, which indicates that a bond is not established at every site where there is metal-to-metal contact. This is attributed to the incomplete breakdown of the oxide film in these areas which may, in turn, be due to a shortage of magnesium within the composite matrix and/or lack of sufficient metal-to-metal contact at the joint interface.

Studies of the effect of specimen deformation on the bond strength showed that the shear strength of the joints was the same, ~50 MPa, for deformations of 2% and 8%, but that it increased to ~120 MPa when the sample was deformed by 19%. This is attributed to (a) greater flattening of the composite surfaces to give more intimate contact, and (b) increased overlap area of the joint (evidenced by barrelling of the sample) to result in greater fragmentation of the alumina film. The fact that the measured shear strength for the sample deformed by 19% lies between the upper- and lower-bound values (135 MPa and 90 MPa, respectively) indicates that the bond is fully established where there are regions of metal-to-metal contact. This deformation threshold is slightly lower than the 20% to 30% reported for pressure-welded and roll-bonded commercial-purity aluminium [8] because the very short periods of time (several seconds) involved with the latter processes relied more on instantaneous friction welding than on interdiffusion of aluminium. Normally, large deformations are to be avoided when processing MMCs as unwanted reinforcement damage may occur, although particulate-reinforced composites, which already contain short reinforcement, would be an ideal candidate for a secondary fabrication process that combines diffusion bonding with some sort of metal forming.

4.2.2. Bonding 2124/P composites with an aluminium alloy (2124) interlayer

The higher strength obtained when bonding unreinforced aluminium alloy (2124) suggested it would be advantageous to use an aluminium alloy (2124) interlayer when bonding together 2124/30P composites. The result was a joint with a shear strength of ~110 MPa, compared with ~45 MPa for a composite bonded without an interlayer. This improvement is due to an increase in the effective bonded area of the joint due to a decrease in the amount of SiC-to-SiC contact, Figures 8a and 8b. Only metal-to-metal regions may form a bond and, as shown previously, lower- and upper-bound values of bond strength may be calculated as ~70 MPa and ~125 MPa, respectively. The introduction of an unreinforced alloy interlayer to increase the proportion of the metal-to-metal contact gives a predicted strength of ~125 MPa, close to the measured shear strength of ~110 MPa.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The presence of magnesium was a crucial factor in forming a solid-state bond since, by disrupting the surface alumina film, it enabled diffusion to take place across the interface. For the particulate composite the shear strength was shown to be inversely proportional to the volume fraction of SiC. The use of an interlayer improved the bond strength by increasing the metal-to-metal contact across the joint, although the value was less than the unreinforced alloy bonded under identical conditions. Results showed that the bond strength could be increased also by using higher deformations due to an increase in contact between the mating surfaces caused by disruption of the oxide films.

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Figure 1. Schematic of shear jig.

Figure 2. Bonded 2124 alloy, OM.

Figure 3. Bonded 2124 alloy.
 a. Particles at interface, TEM.
 b. EDS of interface.
 c. EDS away from interface.

Figure 4. Bonded 2124/25P composite.
 a. Section of joint, OM.
 b. Fracture surface, SEI.

Figure 5. 2124/30P composite bonded with a 2124 alloy interlayer.

Figure 6. Models used for predicting strength of bonded 2124/P composite.
 a. Upper-bound, complete SiC overlap.
 b. Lower-bound, no SiC overlap.

Figure 7. Experimental and predicted data for bonded 2124/P composites.

Figure 8. Schematic representation of the metal-to-metal contact for bonded 2124/P composite.
 a. Without an interlayer (~15%).
 b. With an interlayer (~40%).